

Effect of Different Salt Concentration On the Fermenting Organisms Isolated from *Citrullus Vulgaris* Sample

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ABSTRACT:

The effect of sodium chloride (NaCl) on the organisms isolated from fermented melon seeds in the production of 'ogiri' was studied. The organisms isolated were *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Lactobacillus brevis*, and *Lactobacillus casei*. All the organisms were sensitive to the salt because there was an initial decrease in growth measured in form of optical density. *Staphylococcus* spp., which had been shown to be salt tolerant, grew at high salt concentration thus there were increased in growths on the third day. At higher salt concentration of 2M, there was a drastic reduction in growth. *Bacillus* spp. and *Escherichia coli* are not halotolerant and thus their growth was inhibited at low salt concentration. A 2M salt concentration is therefore recommended for the preservation of the condiment.

Keyword: Ogiri (*Citrullus vulgaris*), salt concentration, Fermenting organisms, Fermentation, sodium chloride.

INTRODUCTION

Fermentation is usually carried out in a moist solid state involving contact with appropriate microorganism at the ambient temperatures; the completion of fermentation is indicated by formation of mucilage and overtones of ammonia produced as a result of breakdown of amino acids during fermentation [1]. 'Ogiri' is one of the condiments consumed in the Eastern and Western parts of Nigeria, especially the 'Ijebu' ethnic groups. It is an oily paste produced by fermenting melon seeds (*Citrullus vulgaris*) in the western part of Nigeria. This food condiment is characterized with very strong pungent odour. Among the consumer, there are preferences for 'ogiri' produced from specific locality [2]. The production process being a local art makes the quality of product varies. The fermented products are also stored at ambient temperature (28±2) °C for varied length of time (days or weeks). The fermentation of the melon seeds is a complex microbiological process involving interactions between quite different microorganisms [3]. The microorganisms use the nutritional components of the seeds, converting them into products that contribute to the chemical composition and taste of the condiment. Quite a number of *Bacillus* spp have been isolated from various food condiments though other bacteria are present. Non-fermenting organisms which are contaminants have also been isolated in appreciable numbers [4]

The population and types of microorganisms involved during fermentation and storage could have affected the quality of the product [2]. The production process is still a traditional family art and the fermentation is by chance inoculation (5). 'Ogiri' serves as a cheap soup condiment particularly among the poor rural dwellers. In the South-East Nigeria, 'ogiri' can also be produced from castor oil seeds *Ricinus cummunis* [6] and fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*) [7]. In recent years, the use of fermented food condiments and flavouring agents are becoming popular in the diets of many nations. Apart from the fact that condiments improve sensory properties of foods, they add to the nutritional values providing dietary fibre, energy, minerals and vitamins [8]. Some of them contain antioxidants and nutraceuticals that provide health benefits. The traditional fermentation of castor oil bean seed into *ogiri* has been reported to be accomplished by mainly bacteria especially *Bacillus* species notably *B. subtilis*, *B. pumillus* and *B. licheniformis* [9; 10]. *Bacillus* species are known specifically for their ability to

initiate fermentation of both nitrogenous and carbohydrate products [11]. The presence of these microbes in such fermentation supports their ubiquitous nature. Being a local art, contamination of Ogiri by pathogenic organisms is a major public health problem. Foodborne diseases are endemic in many developing countries and constitute a major cause of mortality in these areas [12]. Preservation of this food condiment is necessary to extend its shelf-life and to reduce the moisture content. The common ways of preserving this condiment are drying and smoking [13]. These methods of preservation have some limitations associated with them so there is need for another means of preservation. Lime and sodium chloride are additives used in some cultural settings to control the natural fermentation of legume condiments and are known to impact a preservative effect on the end product [14]. Salt is effective as a preservative because it reduces the water activity of foods. The water activity of a food is the amount of unbound water available for microbial growth and chemical reactions. Salt's ability to decrease water activity is thought to be due to the ability of sodium and chloride ions to associate with water molecules [15]. Adding salt to foods can also cause microbial cells to undergo osmotic shock, resulting in the loss of water from the cell and thereby causing cell death or retarded growth [16]. It has also been suggested that for some microorganisms, salt may limit oxygen solubility, interfere with cellular enzymes, or force cells to expend energy to exclude sodium ions from the cell, all of which can reduce the rate of growth [17]. The objective of this study was to investigate the effects of different salt (NaCl) concentrations on preservation of Ogiri.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Sample:

Freshly prepared Ogiri samples were bought from local market in Ekiti (South-West, Nigeria). The samples were transported to the laboratory in cellophane bags and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C.

Microbiological analysis:

Five grams of Ogiri was diluted serially in ten dilution blanks and properly mixed with sterile glass rod. Then 0.1ml of diluted sample was pipette into sterile plate and molten sterile agar medium (45°C) was poured. The media used are nutrient agar and MRS agar. This was done in duplicate and the plates were incubated at 37°C according to the method of Barrow et al. [18].

Characterization of isolates:

Pure cultures of the bacteria isolates were obtained by repeated streaking on nutrient agar. Morphological characteristics of the isolates were examined. For the purpose of identification, the isolates were subjected to biochemical tests such as gelatin hydrolysis, catalase, indole, nitrate reduction, methyl red and sugar utilization according to the method of Olutiola, [19].

Assessment of preservative activity

The salt, (NaCl) was prepared at varied concentrations (0.2M 0.4M 0.6M 0.8M 1.0M 1.2M 1.4M 1.6M 1.8M and 2.0M). 5ml of the salt solution was added to the basal medium for each salt concentration. These were sterilized by autoclaving. Cooled salt-medium solutions were inoculated with 5g of 'ogiri'. Inoculated flasks were incubated in a Brunswick gyrotary shaker incubator at 37°C and 200rpm. Sterile uninoculated broth served as blank. Optical densities were measured at 1day interval for 3days using spectrophotometer at 540nm.

MEASUREMENT OF BACTERIAL GROWTH

Inoculated flasks were incubated in a New Brunswick gyrotary shaker incubator at 37°C and 200rpm. Sterile uninoculated broth serves as blank. Optical densities were measured at 1day interval for 3days (after 24hrs of incubation) using a Pye Unicam SP6-250 Spectrophotometer at 540nm.

Table 1: preservative activity of brine on 'ogiri'

Concentration (M)	Growth in form of Optical density		
	Day 1	Day 2	Day3
0.2	2.136	1.998	2.254
0.4	1.712	1.242	1.664
0.6	1.920	1.560	2.386
0.8	1.623	1.049	1.664
1.0	0.830	1.780	1.356
1.2	1.372	1.053	1.687
1.4	1.458	1.360	1.696
1.6	0.775	1.003	1.443
1.8	0.733	0.954	1.157
2.0	0.930	0.826	0.202

Table 1 shown below indicate preservative activity of brine on ogiri. Microorganisms differ in their tolerance to salt. Some are halotolerant that is; they can grow at a wide range of salt concentration while others are halophiles which can grow only at a high salt concentration. Growth in the tubes was measured in form of optical density. The optical density was plotted against the days of incubation at each salt concentration. The V-shaped graph observed shows that there was an initial decrease in growth followed by an increase in growth. The decrease in growth on the second day could be because some organisms cannot grow under salt concentration and thus are inhibited. Others that can thrive or survive under such condition of salinity will tend to grow more.

At concentration of 1.0M and 2.0M, it was observed that growth was inhibited though not completely. This is because some of the organisms can still withstand such high salt concentration. An example of such organism is *Staphylococcus aureus* and it was isolated from the sample. These concentrations 1.0M and 2.0M can be used in preserving the product though the concentration of 2.0M would be more effective in preserving it.

Results were expressed as means of duplicated determinations. The optical density is a measure of the microbial growth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect to which salt concentration causes changes in bacterial growth depends on the osmotic balance required for such growth. Some bacteria require an astonishingly high level of salt to begin growth, whereas other bacteria would be immediately killed in high levels of salt. The isolates were identified as *Bacillus subtilis*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Lactobacillus* spp. The result is similar to the earlier report by Odunfa [5] that strains of *Bacillus subtilis* are primarily responsible for the fermentation to produce Ogiri. Falegan [2] also proposed that other *Bacillus* spp. ferment the substrate but the Ogiri produced were not of good quality. *Bacillus* might have been introduced by chance inoculation from the air, calabash tray, water used in processing. *E. coli* suggests poor hygienic practices during the production of the condiment. The organism could have been introduced by personnel's utensils and from banana leaves used in wrapping the product. No fungi were isolated and thus Ogiri can be presumed to be free of mycotoxins.

Staphylococcus spp had been shown to be salt tolerant that is they have a high tolerance to chemical preservatives. Haas and Herman (20) reported that two strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* are resistant to a high salt concentration. The growth of *Bacillus subtilis* was inhibited at 8% NaCl (about 1.2M) while that of *Staphylococcus aureus* was at 15% NaCl (about 2.5M) [21]. These previous findings can be used to explain the shape of the graphs. Most of the graphs have a V-shape and this is due to the inhibition of the growth of the *Bacillus* spp causing a decrease in growth on the second day. There was a rise in growth on the third day because of the proliferation of *Staphylococcus aureus* which is halotolerant.

At concentration of 2M, the salt starts having a negative effect on the organisms particularly *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Escherichia coli* was also sensitive to increasing salt concentration thus its growth was inhibited even at low concentrations. Another trend that could be deduced from the table was that as the concentration of salt increases, the microbial growth decreases each day. Also, the isolation of Lactic acid bacteria from the sample is suggestive of acid production in the culture tubes. This can also help keep down the microbial load.

RECOMMENDATION

I am recommending that salt should be used in preserving 'ogiri' so as to overcome the problems associated with the use of drying and smoking.

CONCLUSION

This research work showed that salt could be used in preserving "Ogiri" because the organisms which were associated with the fermentation were sensitive to increase in salt concentrations. Thus, salt can keep down the microbial load of the condiment. Also, isolation of contaminants (pathogenic organisms) showed an unhygienic processing condition, thus good hygiene practices must be undertaken to ensure product's safety.

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